

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PECULIARITIES OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Small and medium enterprises are an important sector of the economy of many countries. Increasing their efficiency means the development of the country to some extent. Research and development of human resource development issues is one of the factors that can be used to achieve the above goal. Therefore, nowadays, research in this direction is relevant and interesting.

The aim of this paper is to study the development of human resources in small and medium-sized enterprises, for which the following tasks were defined: the criteria for defining small and medium-sized businesses are outlined in the article; The priorities of the mentioned field are discussed, the specific issues of human resources development are analyzed and the importance of self-development in the development of managers is emphasized.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is the existing scientific publications on the development of human resources of small and medium-sized enterprises. The issue was studied on the basis of desk research, within which dialectics, analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparison, generalization were used.

The author's assumptions and recommendations are expressed about the issues discussed in the article, thus promoting the effective development of human resources in small and medium-sized businesses. The work will be interesting and useful for researchers interested in studying the mentioned issue and for any interested person.

Keywords: Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs); Human resource development (HRD).

Introduction

The development of human resources in the organization has been the subject of scientific research for many years. Nowadays, organizations no longer dispute that taking care of employee development is a crucial factor. Not only the organization and the employee are interested in it, but also the state, which emphasizes the macroeconomic importance of human resource development (HRD) (Beardwell & Claydon 2007, 257-258).

HRD in business is one of the determinants of competitive advantage, which organizations of different sizes manage differently. Unlike large organizations, employee development in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) varies in intensity, methodology, and many other factors. Therefore, the mentioned issue is relevant and interesting at the modern stage.

Methodology. The aim of the paper is to study the peculiarities of HRD in SMEs. In order to achieve the goal of the research, the document analysis method was used, within the framework of which relevant information was sought. While processing the obtained results, the theoretical and practical aspects of the research question were studied by means of analysis and synthesis techniques.

Main part & findings. The definition and criteria of small, medium (or even large) size enterprises vary according to the legislation of different countries. Most of them are connected only by common criteria: number of employees and turnover. In the case of some countries, we find differentiated criteria according to

fields (for example, Azerbaijan), types of production (for example, Kyrgyzstan), etc.

Human resource management in small enterprises is largely different due to the scale of the business, priorities, informality and the nature of entrepreneurship. It often takes the form of a family business and it is a common practice to combine a number of human resource management issues for an employee of another position (eg owner, assistant, accountant or others). Due to the scale of the small business, the owners (the same entrepreneurs) have close contact with the staff and are involved in business processes, which also manifests itself in a number of human resource management issues (Dessler 2020, 592, 603). Such specificity of small and medium-sized enterprises has a number of advantages and disadvantages, both in HRD and in other directions.

Due to their small scale, small businesses tend to have more information about their employees, which can be used to achieve flexibility in human resource management policies and procedures (Dietz, et al. 2006). Along with flexibility, efficiency also increases, because based on a variety of information, the employer has a better idea about the development needs of the staff, which in turn helps to develop a development plan tailored to the individual.

The priorities for the given sector are also different. Studies show that due to limited resources, they prefer to focus their attention and effort on human resource management, for example, on production, finance, marketing, etc. (McEvoy 1984). In addition, many small business owners prefer a team or family

environment and feel that introducing a formal policy would jeopardize this bond (Marlow 2002). The structural unit of human resources management is also considered a formal event (Katz, et al. 2000). Such an informal and unstructured attitude is often explained by the owner's "control strategy" (Marlow 2002).

Human resource management in many small enterprises takes an informal form, which implies, for example, the informality of staff development. Studies have shown that many of them focus on HRD activities that involve assisting and supervising other employees (Kotey & Folker 2007). The lack of formal staff development activities is often attributed to management expectations because they fear losing trained employees to competitors (Hann 2012). One possible way to avoid such threats is to include "protective" clauses in the employment contract.

Differences in human resources management of small businesses may lead to problems in personnel management, such as: legal risks; Slowing down business processes and high probability of making mistakes by assigning the functions of the human resources management service to other employees; Reduction of competitiveness (Williams 2005). For these and many other reasons, small business employers often turn to outsourcing, which involves using the efforts of professional recruiting organizations, instead of operating an HR department. They are often referred to as personnel leasing companies (Dessler 2020, 603). An alternative to this outsourcing option is for small businesses to hire an HR consultant to help with a range of issues (Dessler 2020, 605). Hiring a new employee is often seen as an alternative to staff learning and development, as it provides new skills and experience (Dundon & Wilkinson 2019). Such decisions, in turn, reduce the opportunities for development and career advancement of existing employees.

The main purpose of training in small businesses is not directed at employees, but focused on the ultimate goal of the business, while training is mostly informal (Gray & Mabey 2005). In general, since small businesses do not have the opportunity to provide the development of human resources with the scale and quality characteristic of large businesses, the available means in this case are online trainings (Dessler 2020, 598). Today, online training websites are very common in the world, which even have users from different countries. The use of such trainings is possible not only for those employed in small businesses, but also within the framework of self-development.

Finally, we should touch on the development of managers. A number of studies reveal that only a small part of managers in small businesses undergo development. The mentioned result is due to the fact that the emphasis is mainly on formal development, however, there are other reasons that are considered as some kind of barriers in management development: lack of time; Scarcity of resources for financing formal training; lack of prior formal education; Doubt about realizing the return on investment in training; lack of information on receiving advice and support; Difficult and bureaucratic barriers in case of application

(Thomson, 2001). Thus, the role of self-development in the development of managers employed in small and medium-sized businesses is especially increasing.

So, human resource development in small and medium-sized businesses is very different, however, this specificity creates an opportunity to discover opportunities that large organizations do not have access to. As we have seen, one such phenomenon is even that small and medium-sized employers have much more information about their employees, and under conditions of reasonable use, information is expensive in business.

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THE CALCULATION METHODOLOGY OF PROVISION OF SANITARIAN RESIDENTIAL PREMISES OF KAZAKHSTAN ENTERPRISES

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МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ РАСЧЕТА ЗАТРАТ НА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ САНИТАРНО-БЫТОВЫМИ ПОМЕЩЕНИЯМИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ КАЗАХСТАНА

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Abstract

The article considers the methodology for calculating the costs of providing sanitarian residential premises and devices. Calculation formulas with explanations are presented. An example of calculating the costs of this direction is given. The cost of providing sanitarian residential premises and devices is an important part of the budget for labor protection.

Аннотация

В статье рассмотрена методика расчета затрат на обеспечение санитарно-бытовыми помещениями и устройствами. Представлены формулы расчета с пояснениями. Приведен пример расчета затрат данного направления. Затраты на обеспечение санитарно-бытовыми помещениями и устройствами являются важной составляющей частью бюджета на охрану труда.

Keywords: sanitarian residential premises, costs, labor protection

Ключевые слова: санитарно-бытовые помещения, затраты, охрана труда

Введение

Вопросы создания безопасных и достойных условий труда на предприятиях являются ключевыми в деятельности любого хозяйствующего субъекта, независимо от форм собственности.

Согласно пункту 1 статьи 181 Трудового кодекса РК работник имеет право на обеспечение санитарно-бытовыми помещениями, средствами индивидуальной и коллективной защиты в соответствии с требованиями по безопасности и охране труда, а также трудовым, коллективным договорами. Обеспечение санитарно-бытового и лечебно-профилактического обслуживания работников возлагается на работодателя [1].

В состав санитарно-бытовых помещений входят: гардеробные, душевые, умывальные, уборные, курительные, места для размещения устройств питьевого водоснабжения, помещения для обогрева или охлаждения, обработки, хранения и выдачи спецодежды, помещения личной гигиены женщин. Площади отдельных санитарно-бытовых помещений, набор оборудования и процедур решается в каждом конкретном случае с учетом мощности объекта, характера трудовых процессов, наличия вредных производственных факторов [2].

Санитарно-эпидемиологические требования к